

Studies on the Suppression of Polarographic Maximum of Ga(III) by Some Uni- and Polyvalent Anions vis-a-vis the Kinetics of the Electrode Reaction

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The suppression of the polarographic negative maximum of Ga(III) has been attempted using some uni- and polyvalent anions, viz., Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_2^- , CNS^- , SO_4^{2-} , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, citrate³⁻ and $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ as suppressors. The extent to which the electrode reaction of Ga(III) is rendered more irreversible from the position in the absence of suppressors (anions), at the point of just suppression is suggested as the criterion for determining the efficacy of a suppressor. Based on this approach the following order of efficacies of uni- and polyvalent anions in the suppression of the negative maximum of Ga(III) has been established :

IN continuation of our earlier report¹ on the suppression of polarographic negative maximum of Ga(III) by some uni- and polyvalent cations, we now report the results of our investigations on the suppression of this maximum by some uni- and polyvalent anions vis-a-vis the kinetics of the electrode reaction.

The experimental details were all the same as reported earlier¹.

Results and Discussion

The first kind polarographic maximum of Ga(III) under the chosen experimental conditions appears at -1.40V (vs SCE) and thus lies well on the negative side of the potential of the electrocapillary zero under the same experimental conditions. Since the $E_{1/2}$ of Ga(III) also lies on the negative side of the electrocapillary zero, the maximum of Ga(III) is of negative polarity^{2(a)}.

A perusal of Table 1 shows that E_{max} gets shifted to positive potentials with increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent anions.

Thus the adsorptive anions (those used here) shift the electrocapillary maximum to less negative potentials^{2(b)} (positive shift) and deform the negative side of the electrocapillary parabola so that the surface tension for any applied potential is lower than the one in the absence of these ions. In other words, for the same surface tension a lower applied potential is needed. Thus, if any such adsorptive anion is successful in suppressing a negative maximum of the first kind, a gradual positive shift of the maximum prior to the final suppression seems to be a necessary prerequisite. Malik and Haque³ observed that the efficacy of a suppressor decreases

as the distance of the maximum from the electrocapillary zero is increased. Since the addition of adsorptive anions causes a positive shift of the electrocapillary zero, the positive shift of the maximum by the addition of these ions on the way to the final elimination of the maximum is consistent with the observation of Malik and Haque. After the suppression of the maximum by the requisite amounts of uni- and polyvalent anions, Ga(III) yields in each case a well-defined and diffusion-controlled wave as is shown by the linearity of i_d vs $h_{\text{corr}}^{1/2}$ plots and their passing through the origin.

Influence of increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent anions on the kinetics of the irreversible electrode reaction of Ga(III) :

Various criteria^{4(a),5,6} for ascertaining the irreversibility of the polarographic reduction of Ga(III) in the presence of increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent anions were applied. These indicated the irreversible nature of the polarographic reduction of Ga(III).

The kinetic parameters (αn_a and $K_{r,h}^2$) have been calculated by Koutecky's method^{7,8} at the point of just suppression of the maximum of Ga(III) and beyond it. A perusal of Table 1 shows that the product αn_a decreases with increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent anions. The values of αn_a give a measure of the extent to which the kinetics of the electrode reaction of Ga(III) is being influenced in the presence of various anions. An attempt to estimate n_a apparently leads⁹ to a conclusion that n_a is equal to 1 in the case of Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_2^- , CNS^- , SO_4^{2-} and $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, (the values of αn_a lie in the range 0.39-0.50 at the stage of just suppression of the maximum) and is equal to 2 in the case of citrate³⁻ and $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ (the values of $\alpha n_a \approx 0.58$)

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TABLE I—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE ELECTRODE REACTION OF Ga(III) IN THE PRESENCE OF INCREASING CONCENTRATIONS OF UNI- AND POLYVALENT ANIONS

[Ga³⁺]=1.0×10⁻⁵M, [NaNO₃]=0.1M, m^{2/3}t^{1/6}=2.03 mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/6} (open circuit, in 0.1 M NaNO₃),
h_{corr}=71.45 cm, temp.=25±0.1°

[Anion] (M)	-E _{max} V (SCE)	-E _{1/2} V (SCE)	i _{max} (μA)	i _d (μA)	Slope (mV)	D×10 ⁶ (cm ² /sec)	α _{na}	k _{f,h} ^o (cm/sec)
0	1.40	—	56.75	—	—	—	—	—
×10 ¹				Cl ⁻				
1.2	1.40	—	55.73	—	—	—	—	—
2.0	1.32	—	23.45	—	—	—	—	—
3.0	1.30	—	11.55	—	—	—	—	—
*3.2	No max	1.168	—	10.19	138	5.62	0.39	8.62×10 ⁻¹⁰
4.8	"	1.205	—	9.18	145	4.55	0.37	3.38×10 ⁻¹⁰
6.4	"	1.245	—	7.81	150	3.30	0.36	2.44×10 ⁻¹⁰
				Br ⁻				
1.0	1.38	—	46.21	—	—	—	—	—
2.0	1.36	—	27.86	—	—	—	—	—
2.8	1.34	—	10.87	—	—	—	—	—
*3.0	No max	1.175	—	9.17	125	4.55	0.42	2.69×10 ⁻¹¹
4.8	"	1.190	—	7.48	130	3.02	0.40	8.53×10 ⁻¹³
14.4	"	1.262	—	6.12	136	2.02	0.32	8.98×10 ⁻¹⁴
				I ⁻				
1.0	1.34	—	25.82	—	—	—	—	—
1.3	1.30	—	17.67	—	—	—	—	—
1.6	1.28	—	12.23	—	—	—	—	—
*1.8	No max	1.140	—	9.17	100	4.55	0.45	2.61×10 ⁻¹²
4.8	"	1.150	—	6.46	105	2.25	0.40	6.21×10 ⁻¹⁴
6.4	"	1.160	—	5.44	112	1.59	0.36	1.47×10 ⁻¹⁴
				NO ₂ ⁻				
1.0	1.36	—	41.45	—	—	—	—	—
1.1	1.34	—	32.28	—	—	—	—	—
1.6	1.30	—	12.23	—	—	—	—	—
*1.7	No max	1.168	—	10.87	115	6.38	0.46	4.86×10 ⁻¹²
3.0	"	1.170	—	9.17	120	4.54	0.43	2.52×10 ⁻¹²
5.0	"	1.200	—	7.82	130	3.31	0.38	1.09×10 ⁻¹²
				CNS ⁻				
0.2	1.40	—	54.71	—	—	—	—	—
0.6	1.34	—	26.84	—	—	—	—	—
1.0	1.28	—	12.23	—	—	—	—	—
*1.3	No max	1.120	—	9.51	130	5.25	0.47	6.70×10 ⁻¹⁰
2.4	"	1.170	—	8.15	140	3.59	0.43	1.11×10 ⁻¹⁰
4.8	"	1.180	—	6.12	152	2.02	0.40	3.13×10 ⁻¹¹
×10 ²				SO ₄ ²⁻				
3.0	1.36	—	26.55	—	—	—	—	—
4.0	1.30	—	11.40	—	—	—	—	—
4.4	1.28	—	9.03	—	—	—	—	—
*4.6	No max	1.178	—	7.23	110	2.82	0.49	5.05×10 ⁻⁹
6.4	"	1.180	—	6.67	115	2.41	0.46	3.98×10 ⁻⁹
12.0	"	1.181	—	5.98	118	1.93	0.42	1.09×10 ⁻⁹
×10 ³				C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻				
0.4	1.40	—	23.21	—	—	—	—	—
0.5	1.30	—	13.45	—	—	—	—	—
0.6	1.24	—	7.23	—	—	—	—	—
*1.4	No max	1.100	—	6.67	105	2.41	0.50	1.11×10 ⁻¹⁰
1.5	"	1.110	—	3.75	113	0.76	0.47	8.36×10 ⁻¹²
1.6	"	1.114	—	3.19	118	0.55	0.45	3.10×10 ⁻¹²
×10 ⁴				Citrate ³⁻				
0.6	1.38	—	23.21	—	—	—	—	—
0.9	1.32	—	14.04	—	—	—	—	—
1.2	1.24	—	5.84	—	—	—	—	—
*1.3	No max	1.080	—	4.45	110	1.07	0.56	6.92×10 ⁻¹⁰
1.6	"	1.130	—	2.64	125	0.38	0.52	3.25×10 ⁻¹²
1.7	"	1.135	—	2.08	132	0.23	0.50	6.21×10 ⁻¹⁴
×10 ⁵				[Fe(ON) ₆] ⁴⁻				
1.2	1.39	—	22.10	—	—	—	—	—
2.4	1.32	—	9.73	—	—	—	—	—
2.8	1.30	—	6.53	—	—	—	—	—
*3.0	No max	1.101	—	3.61	120	0.71	0.58	3.52×10 ⁻¹⁰
3.2	"	1.102	—	3.84	125	0.60	0.53	1.42×10 ⁻¹²
3.5	"	1.105	—	2.78	132	0.42	0.52	4.86×10 ⁻¹²

* Concentration at which the maximum gets just suppressed.

because for totally irreversible systems, as the present one is, α should be less than¹⁰ 0.5. However, according to Meites^(b) only a single electron can be transferred at a time and a value of n_a exceeding 1 should merely mean that the successive steps are too nearly simultaneous to be distinguished on the time scale implicit in the polarographic measurement. Thus, whether n_a is 1 or 2, the change in αn_a values, which at no stage varies by a factor of 2 between successive values, can only be due to a change in α . It is thus concluded that it is α which is decreasing. α , the transfer coefficient, signifies¹¹ the fraction of applied voltage which favours the cathodic reaction, $\text{Ga}^{3+} + 3 e \rightarrow \text{Ga}$. A decrease in the value of α thus implies that the transfer of electron/electrons is made increasingly difficult. In other words, the electrode reaction of Ga(III) is rendered increasingly more irreversible with increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent anions. A decrease in the value of $k_{r,b}$ (Table 1) with increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent anions lends support to this conclusion. This is further supported by a negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ and a decrease in i_d values (Table 1) with increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent anions.

Relative efficacies of uni- and polyvalent anions in the suppression of the maximum of Ga(III) on the basis of αn_a values :

At the stage where the maximum of Ga(III) just disappears, the order of αn_a values signifies¹² the extent to which the addition of uni- and polyvalent anions renders the electrode reaction of Ga(III) more irreversible from the stage when no suppressor (anion) is added. In other words an anion for which αn_a has got a higher value at the point of just

suppression will be more effective with minimum influence on the kinetics of the electrode reaction of Ga(III). On this basis, the following order of efficacies of various uni- and polyvalent anions has been established : $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-} > \text{citrate}^{3-} > \text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-} > \text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{CNS}^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{I}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{Cl}^-$. Thus, $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ eliminates the maximum of Ga(III) with minimum influence on the kinetics of the electron-transfer followed by citrate³⁻, $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, SO_4^{2-} , CNS^- , NO_3^- , I^- , Br^- and Cl^- .

It is interesting to note that uni- and polyvalent anions follow the valency rule. Further, the order of relative efficacies found on the basis of αn_a values in respect of uni- and polyvalent anions is identical with that obtained on the basis of molarity scale.

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